

Panic of Corona and Psychological Grief among Teachers after Returning to Teaching under the Corona PandemicAmrita Chauhan¹, Rajesh Singh², Jugendra Lahari³, Sachin Singh Yadav⁴, Ashish Saraswat⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, GMC, Datia (M.P.)²Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, GMC, Datia (M.P.)³Senior Resident, Department of Medicine, GMC, Datia (M.P.)⁴Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, GMC, Datia (M.P.)⁵Senior Resident, Department of Microbiology and Infectious Diseases, MLBMC, Jhansi (U.P.)

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Abstract:**Background and Objectives:** Two psychological effects of the corona virus's propagation that were identified in much earlier study were teachers' anxiety of the virus and their psychological unease after returning to the classroom. As teachers return to face-to-face instruction, the current study seeks to determine the level of psychological anguish, fear of Corona, and the relationship between the two.**Methods:** After receiving their first consent, the questionnaire was delivered to the teachers in various schools after they indicated that they would take part in filling it out. They were made aware of the study's objectives, including all moral concerns with maintaining the privacy of the data and the fact that the data would only be utilized for scientific research. As a result, 300 teachers were given the questionnaire using a basic random sample procedure.**Results:** The study was female preponderance with 54% are female teachers and most common age group was 30-39 years comprising 45% participants followed by 40-49 years. There are no statistically significant differences in the level of fear of Corona among the teachers, which is due to the variable of gender. There are no statistically significant differences at the significance level of in the level of psychological distress among the teachers according to the variable of age.**Conclusion:** The study found a strong correlation between psychological discomfort and fear of Corona. The development of the teachers' flexibility and emotional adaptability is essential to bolstering their non-knowledge abilities and protecting them from the negative impacts of the phenomena of fear and psychological distress.**Keywords:** Panic of Corona, Psychological grief, Depression, Stress, Anxiety.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Because to the COVID-19 pandemic, we no longer perceive the world as we once did. Strong social isolation and lockdown measures put in place since the start of the epidemic have had a significant negative impact on social connections, which has left many individuals feeling lonely and alone. Indeed, the social, psychological, economic, and educational results of individuals have been impacted by the rapid proliferation of COVID-19 around the world. [1] In actuality, the global closure of schools in order to reduce illnesses has been one of the most commonly used techniques for increasing social segregation.

With the spread of the pandemic, experts began to emphasize how important it is to maintain both physical and mental health. The fear of developing

the illness, enduring its difficult symptoms, and losing their family negatively impacted people's psychological and social well-being. An increase in the severity of psychological conditions, an increase in the use of alcohol, tobacco, and narcotics, and an increase in the danger of death even among medical professionals were only a few of the symptoms brought on by the fear and stress linked with COVID-19. [2]

Beyond the mental health of the students, the epidemic's spread and impacts had a serious detrimental effect on the teachers as well. The need to swiftly adapt to teaching kids online during the shutdown period reportedly caused stress for teachers, according to many studies. The limitations imposed had an effect on their positions and

orientations, which in turn had an effect on their worries and convictions, methods of adapting, and other day-to-day issues. [3]

These difficulties force the teachers to adapt to new modes of instruction. This experience had several psychological impacts, including terror. They struggled to strike a balance between their professional and personal commitments, faced stress from having to meet criteria in a novel environment, such as using educational technology, and expressed fear for the future. Therefore, the mental distress could be very severe. [4]

Teaching is a very demanding profession, especially when working with teenagers. According to studies, as a result of COVID-19, 17% of teachers experience fear, 19% experience despair, and 33% experience tiredness.

UNESCO (2020) noted that one of the negative effects of closing the schools is a situation of uncertainty and stress among the teachers due to the abrupt interruptions of these closures, the lack of information regarding the duration of closure, and the generally limited understanding of remote learning. [6]

Understanding the psychological alterations that COVID-19 generates, such as unpleasant emotions, knowledge indications, and social hazards, is crucial since it may have a detrimental effect on a person's psychological health. The cause of each of these modifications is COVID-19.

Materials and Methods

After receiving their first consent, the questionnaire was delivered to the teachers in various schools after they indicated that they would take part in filling it out. They were made aware of the study's objectives, including all moral concerns with maintaining the privacy of the data and the fact that the data would

only be utilized for scientific research. As a result, 300 teachers in the were given the questionnaire using a basic random sample procedure.

Methodology

Utilizing the Measure of Fear of Corona, the psychometric validity and reliability coefficients were computed. There were seven items in the assessment. The five-grade Lickert scale was used to adjust the measurement. Its grades are (I strongly disagree: 1, I disagree; 2, I don't agree; and do not disagree: 3, I agree; 4, I firmly agree; and 5). According to a scale with grades ranging from 7 to 35, the highest score denotes the presence of dread of the corona virus.

The Psychological Distress Measure (DASS-21), a condensed form of the full DASS, was used in the current investigation. There are 21 items in the assessment. It comprises of three tests used to gauge stress, anxiety, and depression. It is a self-report test designed to assess cases of emotional stress, anxiety, and depression. Each measure consists of seven items: three for depression (items 3, 5, 10, 13, 16, and 21), four for anxiety (items 2, 4, 7, 9, 15, and 20), and three for stress (items 1, 6, 8, 11, 12, and 14).

Statistical Analysis

The resulting data were statistically analyzed. Version 22.0 of SPSS software was used to analyze the data. The data were described using descriptive statistical analysis, which included frequency and percentages. For the study's several dependent variables, inferential statistics included the chi-square test and the independent samples t test, with a p value of 0.05 being deemed statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Age and Gender wise distribution of teachers

Variable		Number	Percentage %	Total
Gender	Male	140	40	300
	Female	160	60	
Age	20- 29	40	13	300
	30-39	150	50	
	40- 49	70	24	
	50 and Over	40	13	

As per table 1 the study was female preponderance with 60% are female teachers and most common age group was 30-39 years comprising 50% participants followed by 40-49 years.

Table 2: Classification of Psychological distress

Severity of Symptoms	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
Normal	0-4	0-3	0-7
Mild	5-6	4-5	8-9
Moderate	7-10	6-7	10-12
Severe	11-13	8-9	13-16
Extremely Severe	14+	10+	17+

As per table 2 psychological distresses was calculated by using DASS-21 scale. The degrees are specified on the branch measures (depression, anxiety, and stress) to classify the intensity of the symptoms from light to extremely severe.

Table 3: Fear of Corona in teachers according to gender variable

Variable	Gender	Number	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
The total degree of fear of corona	Male	140	21.13	7.05	.07
	Female	160	22.65	6.15	

As per table 3 that there are no statistically significant differences in the level of fear of Corona among the teachers, which is due to the variable of gender. The arithmetic mean for the total degree among the males was (21.13), while the arithmetic means for the females was 22.65.

Table 4: Psychological distress in teachers according to gender variable

Variable	Gender	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
Depression	Male	140	5.51	4.18	0.14
	Female	160	4.15	4.25	
Anxiety	Male	140	5.16	4.36	0.01*
	Female	160	4.18	3.46	
Stress	Male	140	5.42	4.50	0.09
	Female	160	4.43	4.62	
The total degree of psychological distress	Male	140	17.27	13.71	0.01*
	Female	160	13.13	11.99	

As per table 4 there are statistically significant differences in the level of psychological distress among the teachers, which are due to the variable of gender on the total degree and the dimension of depression and anxiety in favour of the males, while it is indicated that there are no differences on the two dimensions of depression and stress.

Table 5: Fear of Corona among teachers according to age

Variable	Age	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
Fear of Corona	20-29	40	22.33	6.30	0.63
	30-39	150	24.80	7.32	
	40-49	70	23.28	7.12	
	50 and over	40	23.58	7.04	

As per table 5 there are no statistically significant differences for the level of fear of Corona among the teachers according to the variable of age.

Table 6: Psychological distress in teachers according to age variable

Variable	Age	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
Depression	20-29	40	6.04	5.63	0.20
	30-39	150	5.02	4.85	
	40-49	70	4.89	4.17	
	50 and over	40	4.18	4.59	
Anxiety	20-29	40	5.29	4.96	0.31
	30-39	150	4.11	3.91	
	40-49	70	4.16	3.97	
	50 and over	40	5.61	4.47	
Stress	20-29	40	6.91	4.84	0.22
	30-39	150	5.68	4.37	
	40-49	70	4.02	3.82	
	50 and over	40	5.71	4.41	
The total degree of psychological distress	20-29	40	18.25	14.49	0.14
	30-39	150	15.82	11.12	
	40-49	70	13.08	11.08	
	50 and over	40	15.51	12.89	

As per table 6 that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level of in the level of psychological distress among the teachers according to the variable of age. And there

is an approximation in the level of psychological distress given the differences in their ages.

Discussion

The Corona pandemic had an immediate effect on the military troops serving on the front lines, especially the teachers. The current study is out to measure teachers' psychological distress and corona fear levels. In order for teachers to keep providing educational services in the event of an emergency or the spread of a disease, this research will help us understand how to protect them. The results of the survey suggested that there was no apprehension about Corona. This is in line with the research's conclusions. [7,8] This might be because young people, who made up the majority of the study's sample, had higher levels of awareness and knowledge, were better able to use personal protection techniques, and possessed psychological processes and character traits that made dealing with health risks easier for them. This society has emphasized the significance of using healthy methods to fight the epidemic, which were outlined in calls from the mosques as a religious requirement for which man is responsible, as well as the significance of human readiness for all outcomes, particularly that readiness for the epidemic. Religion provides a sense of comfort and lessens worry and dread. Previous studies that discovered beneficial correlations between religious activity and wellbeing stressed this. Other research, however, has shown that religion plays no part in reducing the fear of Corona. [9] Because different nations have different standards for determining the degree of awareness and comprehension regarding this condition, the findings of past study may have varied. The finding that fear levels were higher in Corona than elsewhere acted as a reminder of this. [8,9] But various results from earlier study were obtained. In Berlin, a cross-sectional study conducted in the summer of 2020 found that 59% of the student squad reported having a medium-to-high concern of contracting the disease. A medium to very severe fear to dread of the virus was stated by half of the crew. [10]

The study uncovered that 73% of the teachers were afraid of being infected by SARS-CoV-2 in the school and that the females were more worried than the males. This agrees with the fact that women are more vulnerable to being infected with anxiety than men. According to the study's findings, there were no changes in the sample's level of psychological discomfort according to age. However, the results indicated that the amount of fear was higher in younger people and decreased with age. In other studies, it was noted that those between the ages of 30 and 39 who felt more distress had higher levels of fear. However, prior research revealed that those over the age of 47 have increased levels of anxiety and fatigue. [11] The pandemic caused the teachers a lot of stress. This may be a result of their inability to adjust to remote learning

and their worry about their future as a result of the epidemic. As a result, there may be serious mental anguish among them. The earlier investigations also showed that people's lives are harmed by their dread of Corona. [12]

The results of the current study are astounding, nevertheless, in that men displayed greater anxiety than women. These findings conflict with those of recent studies, which show that women tend to experience anxiety on average more than men. The current investigation demonstrated that there are no age-related changes in psychological discomfort. This outcome appears to be at odds with the study on age-related distress. This finding appears to be at odds with the study's finding that older teachers experienced higher levels of stress and anxiety. This may be because it is challenging to adjust to the technology techniques that will be employed in education. However, the study found that among instructors, age was not significantly associated with tension, anxiety, or depression; older teachers and those with more experience report less stress. [12]

Conclusion

The relevance of being interested in this area is made clear by this study, which found a connection between psychological distress and Corona phobia. It is important to improve the non-knowledge skills of teachers, such as flexibility and emotional adaptation, to strengthen their psychological immunity and protect them from the negative effects of the phenomena of fear and psychological distress. This is because the quality of the teaching services that are provided to the students and the quality of the students' emotional states are both influenced by the teachers' emotional states. As a result, it is inevitable to focus on providing psychological and social support for them as well as creating psychological and social techniques and interventions that can be applied in the event of crises like the Corona crisis. The study suggests carrying out research with additional factors like spirituality, religiosity, and personality qualities.

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